

DISPLAY OF JOY'S MULTIDIMENSIONALITY IN ENGLISH PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS-MOTIVES

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ABSTRACT

This work is devoted to the study of the means of phraseological representation of emotive concepts in Russian and English on the example of the concept "joy". The work was carried out within the framework of cognitive phraseology, a modern direction linguistics, and is aimed at investigating the problem of the relationship between linguistic units and cognitive structures of knowledge representation in the aspect of phraseological conceptualization of selected emotions.

Key words: *Linguistics, concept, phraseology, joy, happiness, cognitive, structure, world picture, emotion.*

The English language has a thousand-year history. During this time, a large number of expressions have accumulated in it, which people found successful, accurate and beautiful. This is how a special layer of language emerged – phraseology, a set of stable expressions that have an independent meaning. Learning English is widespread in our country. A good knowledge of the language, including English, is impossible without knowledge of its phraseology. Knowledge of phraseology makes it extremely easy to read both journalistic and fiction literature. Reasonable use of phraseological units makes speech more expressive. With the help of phraseological expressions that are not translated verbatim, but are perceived reinterpreted, the aesthetic aspect of the language is enhanced.

The experience of emotional states of joy and happiness is reduced to the general semantics of "elated mood". Joy causes a person to have a cheerful mood, he

experiences a state of pleasure, inner satisfaction. Happiness causes a strong surge of joy when a person experiences a state of the highest satisfaction, inner harmony with the world. Happiness is closely related to joy

The state of happiness and joy is also transmitted to the FAIRY through the image of the sky of extraordinary height and purity, the perfection of which is expressed by the numerals seven, less often nine: to be in the seventh heaven of happiness, the head reaches to the sky; from earth to heaven – to be very happy; to be at the top of bliss in HEAVEN and be in seventh heaven – to be on the seventh heaven of happiness; feel on the top of the world – to be on top of happiness (lit. feel on top of the world); on cloud seven (or nine) – infinitely happy, in the seventh heaven; the dizzy height – a dizzying height, a great success in English.

Happiness can be judged by the sparkle in the eyes: the eyes laugh – shine with joy – about the eyes; the eyes and soul open – have fun in the eyes and be bright-eyed and bushy tailed – be full of energy and strength (letters. be with bright eyes and a fluffy tail) in English. PhU with the "eyes" component are significantly more represented in the Russian than in the English.

Both in the Russian and in the English, PhU have been identified, the basis of which is related to the image of a rose, pink, red and white flowers: to live like a rose – to spend happy days; to see everything, the world in pink light (color); paradise (pink) in the garden and a bed of roses – a serene, happy life (lit. bed of roses); see (look) through rose-colored glasses – look through rose-colored glasses; red-letter day – red calendar day, festive, happy day; the white hen's chock – lucky (lit. white chicken chicken) in English.

In the figurative basis of the following PhU of this subgroup, the soul and the heart are basic metaphors: to add a soul to the soul – to please; to make it is pleasant to the soul – to please, to give pleasure; to stroke the soul – to please; to rejoice (rejoice) in the soul. PhU with the image of the soul were revealed only in the Russian.

Interesting is the fact that the same state the concept of "cold" conveys joy in Russian, and "warm" in English. This is explained by the background of the occurrence

of a joyful feeling. If in the first case a person finds a state of joy after a certain negative tension, i.e. we are talking about a change of emotional state, then in the latter there is only a positive moment.

We have briefly characterized the figurative-symbolic dominants of Russian and English languages underlying the internal form of phraseological units that implement the conceptual opposition "joy".

Russian and English phraseology conceptualize the emotions studied in many ways the same (cognitive metaphor "top/ bottom", components "heavenly space", "heart", "gold"), but it is also possible to trace the national-specific components (associations with the elements water / air, color characteristics).

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